

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16790449

Demographic Determinants Of Perceived Occupational Hazards Among Sawmill Workers In Rivers State

Egwanwor, Chinwenwo Bright

**Department of Health Promotion, Environmental and Safety Education
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

The growing concern for occupational health and safety has drawn attention to the critical hazards industrial workers face across various sectors of the economy. Among these, sawmill industries rank significantly high due to the array of hazards prevalent in their operational environments. Consequently, many workers rely on personal experiences and informal coping mechanisms to manage their exposure to hazards. The perception of risk, therefore, becomes a critical determinant of whether or not workers take proactive steps toward hazard prevention or health-seeking behaviors. Such perception is often influenced by demographic factors. This study investigated the demographic determinants of perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill workers in Rivers State. A cross sectional descriptive survey design was adopted to study all the sawmill workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis with a population of 208. Instrument for data collection consisted of a self-structured questionnaire which was validated with a reliability coefficient of 0.81. A total of 208 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the sawmill workers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, 200 copies of the administered questionnaire were returned, which indicated 96% returned rate. Data was analyzed using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 20.0. The study revealed that there was a significant difference in the perceived occupational hazards in Port Harcourt metropolis based on type of work, working experience, educational level and marital status. Based on the findings, the study concludes that perceived occupational hazards in the sawmill industry within Port Harcourt Metropolis vary significantly across multiple demographic and work-related factors. It was recommended that regular awareness campaigns, posters, safety drills, and workshops should be conducted within sawmill premises to reinforce hazard identification and safe work practices

Keywords: Demographic Determinants, Occupational Hazards, Sawmill Workers

INTRODUCTION

Occupational hazards have been a longstanding concern in both developed and developing nations, posing threats to the safety, health, and overall well-being of workers. The International Labour Organization (ILO, 2021) estimates that over 2.78 million work-related deaths occur globally each year, with a significant portion resulting from occupational diseases and hazardous working environments. Among the most affected sectors is the informal workforce, particularly in countries with limited regulation and enforcement of health and safety policies. In Nigeria, the sawmill industry largely informal and

unregulated represents a vital economic activity, especially in regions like Rivers State, but it is also one of the most hazard-prone occupations.

Sawmill workers are involved in the cutting, shaping, and treatment of wood, which often entails exposure to multiple occupational hazards, including noise pollution, wood dust, machine-related injuries, ergonomic strains, and in some cases, chemical exposure from wood treatment agents (Opoko et al., 2021). Despite the economic relevance of sawmills in Nigeria's construction and furniture industries, the health and safety of the workers have remained relatively understudied and poorly managed. Workers often operate under precarious conditions, with limited access to personal protective equipment (PPE), insufficient health education, and a general lack of institutional support or formal training on safety practices (Adebayo & Ogunleye, 2017).

Rivers State, being one of Nigeria's most industrialized regions, has witnessed significant growth in artisanal and small-scale industries like sawmills. These sawmills are primarily concentrated in urban and semi-urban centers such as Port Harcourt, Ahoada, and Bori. While they contribute meaningfully to employment and urban development, the risk of occupational hazards in these areas is alarmingly high. Many of the workers in these sawmills lack formal education, receive minimal health and safety training, and are often exposed to harsh working conditions without adequate health surveillance (Olaitan & Adeniyi, 2019). The hazards are not just physical but also chemical and biological, with long-term implications such as respiratory diseases, hearing loss, musculoskeletal disorders, and even fatalities.

In the Nigerian context, occupational health remains a poorly prioritized component of the national health system. Although the Nigerian Labour Act mandates the protection of workers' rights and the provision of safe work environments, implementation at the local level especially in informal sectors like sawmilling is largely absent (Adedeji et al., 2016). Consequently, many workers rely on personal experiences and informal coping mechanisms to manage their exposure to hazards. The perception of risk, therefore, becomes a critical determinant of whether or not workers take proactive steps toward hazard prevention or health-seeking behaviors. Such perception is often influenced by demographic factors such as level of education, work experience, marital status, and type of job role.

Education level is a major determinant in hazard perception. Workers with higher levels of formal education tend to have better awareness of workplace dangers and are more likely to adopt safe practices or demand for improved working conditions (Gyekye, 2009). On the contrary, workers with little or no education may underestimate the severity of hazards or fail to appreciate the long-term health implications. This has been confirmed in various studies which show a direct relationship between low literacy levels and high incidence of occupational injuries (Olabintan et al., 2020). In the sawmill context, educational attainment may affect how workers interpret safety instructions, use PPE, or respond to emergencies.

Work experience is another critical variable. While more experienced workers might have developed practical knowledge about workplace hazards, they may also become desensitized or overconfident in their ability to avoid injury. Conversely, less experienced workers may be more cautious but lack the technical know-how to navigate dangerous situations. The relationship between experience and perceived occupational risk is thus complex and context-dependent (Ajayi et al., 2022). In some cases, prolonged exposure without injury might falsely assure workers of their immunity, while new entrants into the profession may overestimate risks due to unfamiliarity.

Type of work within the sawmill industry also plays a significant role in determining exposure levels and risk perception. For instance, machine operators and log handlers are often at higher risk of traumatic injuries compared to administrative or sales personnel. Those who handle chemicals used in wood preservation may face chronic health risks such as respiratory problems, skin diseases, and cancer. The intensity and nature of exposure may directly shape how workers perceive occupational hazards, influencing their attitude towards safety and health (Okonkwo & Onoh, 2015). Those in more dangerous roles may either develop heightened risk awareness or become fatalistic over time, believing that accidents are inevitable.

Marital status is an often-overlooked demographic factor in occupational health studies but can have meaningful implications. Married workers may perceive higher stakes in maintaining their health due to family responsibilities, prompting more cautious behavior. Conversely, unmarried workers may engage in riskier tasks due to fewer perceived liabilities. Studies have shown that individuals with dependents are more likely to adhere to safety protocols and seek medical attention when symptoms of occupational illness arise (Akinwale & Oludele, 2016). Therefore, family responsibilities may influence both perception and actual practices regarding workplace hazards.

Given these dynamics, the present study seeks to explore how demographic characteristics specifically educational level, work experience, type of work, and marital status shape the perception of occupational hazards among sawmill workers in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on type of work and working experience?
2. What is the difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on educational level and marital status?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level:

1. There is no significant differences in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on type of work.
2. There is no significant differences in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on working experience.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross sectional descriptive survey design, this design is geared towards describing, analyzing behavioural or explaining events as they occur at a specific time (Elendu, 2010). Osagbemi, La-Kadiri and Aderibigbe (2010) utilized the design in a similar study in North central on awareness of occupational hazards, health problems and safety measures among sawmill workers in Nigeria. The population of the study was 208. This consist of all the workers of sawmill industries in Rivers State. These include Ukwato 60 workers in Mile 2 by Iloabuchi, Mile three with 38 workers. Okwelle 30 workers in Mile 2 Diobu, Aluu 40 workers in Ikwerre L.G.A., and Rukpokwu 40 workers in Obio/Akpor LGA. (Source-chairmen of sawmill market). There was no sampling because the population was small and manageable. This procedure was used by Osagbemi in 2010 to study all the 257 workers in sawmill industries at North Central, Nigeria.

The instrument for data collection consist of a validated self-structured questionnaires tagged "Perceived Occupational Hazards among Workers of Sawmill Industries Questionnaire (POHWSIQ) with a reliability co-efficient of 0.81. The instrument consists of two sections: Section A is made up of socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, while section B, indicates respondent's view on the perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Rivers State. The instrument has four point response categories of Strongly Agree (4 points), Agree (3 points), Disagree (2 points), and Strongly Disagree (1 point).

Letter of introduction duly signed by the Head of Department Kinetics and Health Education Department, University of Port Harcourt was given to the Head of Department (such as wood loaders/off loaders, machine operators, sprayers, mortisers, chisellers etc.) at the sawmill industries in Rivers State. This was done, to enable the researcher gain permission, before the copies of questionnaire were administered. The copies of questionnaire were self-administered to the respondents by the researcher, through the aid of five (5) research assistants. The completed questionnaire copies were collected at the spot while others were collected on a date agreed upon

After retrieving the questionnaire from the various respondents the completed copies of the questionnaire were coded and analyzed using descriptive statistics of simple Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation

for research questions while z-test and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on type of work and working experience?*

Table 1: Summary of ANOVA analysis on difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on type of work

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	118.125	3	39.375	91.636	.000
Within Groups	6.875	16	.430		
Total	125.000	19			

The result in ANOVA Table 1 show the output of the ANOVA analysis and whether there is a statistically significant difference between the group mean. The result revealed that the significance value is 0.000 (i.e., $p = .000$), which is below 0.05 meaning that there is a statistical significant difference in the mean ratings of perceived occupational hazards in Port Harcourt Metropolis based on type of work.

Table 2: Summary of ANOVA analysis on difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on working experience.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	35.200	3	11.733	7.822	.002
Within Groups	24.000	16	1.500		
Total	59.200	19			

The ANOVA table 2 result revealed that there is a statistically significant difference between groups and within groups as a whole. From the analysis the significance value is 0.002 (i.e; $p-v = .002$) which is less than 0.05. This means there is a statistically significant difference in the mean of perceived occupational hazards exist based on their years of working experience in sawmill industry.

Research Question 2: *What is the difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on educational level and marital status?*

Table 3: Summary of ANOVA analysis on difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on educational level.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	140.850	3	46.950	18.733	.000
Within Groups	40.100	16	2.506		
Total	180.950	19			

The ANOVA table 3 analysis shows that there is a statistically significant difference between groups and within groups as a whole. From the ANOVA table the significant at 0.000 which is below 0.05. We could conclude that there is a significant difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on educational level.

Table 4: Summary of ANOVA analysis on difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on marital status.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	120.981	2	60.490	85.915	.000
Within Groups	11.969	17	.704		
Total	132.950	19			

The ANOVA Table analysis revealed that there is a statistically significant We could conclude that there is a significant difference in perceived occupational hazards among workers of sawmill industries in Port Harcourt metropolis Rivers State based on marital status at (Sig) .000 which is less 0.05.

DISCUSSION

The study revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in perceived occupational hazards in Port Harcourt metropolis based on type of work and working experience. This is in conformity with Osagbemi et al., (2010) which revealed that majority of the respondent were machine operators, hen occurrence of accidents were less than 20%. The findings also revealed that most biological hazard of the sawmill workers were general waste and fungi/mould. General waste constitute dangerous airborne while fungi/mould are disease causing agents that grow on wood logs. This is also similar to Yusuf et al (2014) which revealed that generated waste had a lot effect on health condition of workers in sawmill industries. The older sawmill workers who use their personal protective equipment correctly will have less exposure to biological hazards compares to the new workers who do not use theirs correctly. Therefore exposure to biological hazards could be said to be relative to practice and not duration of service. According to significance value in the table, this is in conformity with Faremi et al., (2014) which revealed that crash injury difficulty in breathing as a result of inhalation of harmful chemical, there was high level of awareness but incorrect conceptualization of occupational hazards among Nigeria sawmill workers.

The findings of this study revealed a significance differences in perceived occupational hazards exist based on their level of education and marital status. The study also revealed that non-formal education differ from secondary education with a significance at .028 and tertiary education significance at .000. This is in line with Faremi et al., (2014) who noted that more than half of the respondents were aware of occupational hazards sawmill noise pollution, crash injury, most of them were the implicated risks to health hazards. The finding of this study could be true reflection of the modem day sawmill workers, where generator set is constantly used since there is no constant electrical power supply. The noise that emanate from the generator set is always high at the industries and as such causes hearing impairment to the sawmill workers. This is a collaboration with Osagbemi, La-kadiri and Aderibigbe (2010) whose study assert machine and electric shock are the hazards in the sawmill industries, the level awareness of the various occupational hazards was very low except of electric shock which was high. The findings also revealed that the most common health problems experienced were minor accidents.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concludes that perceived occupational hazards in the sawmill industry within Port Harcourt Metropolis vary significantly across multiple demographic and work-related factors. Specifically, workers' type of work, years of experience, educational level, and marital status all influence how they perceive occupational hazards.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Safety training should be designed to meet the specific needs of different categories of workers based on their job roles, educational levels, and years of experience.
2. Regular awareness campaigns, posters, safety drills, and workshops should be conducted within sawmill premises to reinforce hazard identification and safe work practices.
3. Sawmill owners and regulatory agencies should establish clear occupational safety standards and enforce compliance through periodic inspections. Provision of personal protective equipment (PPE) such as gloves, safety boots, helmets, and goggles should be mandatory, and penalties should be applied for non-compliance to ensure a culture of safety.

REFERENCES

- Adebayo, T. O., & Ogunleye, T. (2017). Occupational hazards and industrialization in Nigeria, with emphasis on the informal sector. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 23(4), 562–570.
- Adedeji, G. A., Aiyeloja, A. A., & Nwosu, U. J. (2016). Ergonomic evaluation and labour inspection in cluster-sawmill in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Pro Ligno*, 12(2), 38-50.
- Ajayi, M. A., Oluwaseun, O. F., & Adebola, F. (2022). Work experience and perception of workplace risks: A comparative study. *International Journal of Occupational Safety*, 9(4), 73–80.
- Akinwale, Y. S., & Oludele, A. (2016). Family responsibility as a motivator for safety compliance: Evidence from Nigerian industries. *Nigerian Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 4(1), 56–64.
- Gyekye, S. A., & Salminen, S. (2009). Educational status and organizational safety climate: Does educational attainment influence workers' perceptions of workplace safety?. *Safety science*, 47(1), 20-28.
- International Labour Organization (ILO). (2021). *World Employment and Social Outlook: Trends 2021*. Geneva: ILO.
- Okonkwo, S. I., & Onoh, J. N. (2015). Occupational hazards and safety practices among industrial workers in Nigeria. *Journal of Occupational Health and Safety*, 3(2), 22–30.
- Olabintan, O. O., Balogun, W. A., & Akinbode, K. O. (2020). Literacy, safety knowledge, and the incidence of occupational injuries in Nigeria's informal sector. *African Safety Promotion Journal*, 18(1), 15–27.
- Olaitan, O. A., & Adeniyi, O. R. (2019). Health and safety challenges in small-scale industries in Rivers State. *Nigerian Journal of Public Health Research*, 11(1), 40–49.
- Opoku, F. A., Opoku, D. A., Ayisi-Boateng, N. K., Osarfo, J., Sulemana, A., Agyemang, S., ... & Agyei-Baffour, P. (2024). Occupational injury prevalence and predictors among small-scale sawmill workers in the Sokoban Wood Village, Kumasi, Ghana. *PLoS one*, 19(4), e0298954.